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Facile Synthesis and Characterization of Ag/Ag₂S Nanoparticles Enzymatically Grown In Situ and their Application to the Colorimetric Detection of Glucose Oxidase

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Abstract

This work describes a simple, fast and reproducible biochemical reaction to modulate the growth of silver/silver sulfide nanoparticles (Ag/Ag₂S NPs) through the enzymatic activity of the glucose oxidase (GOx). This process occurs in aqueous buffered solutions at room temperature under physiological conditions with participation of inexpensive precursors. Oxidation of 1-thio-β-D-glucose is catalyzed by GOx yielding hydrogen sulfide. Direct interaction between silver nitrate and enzymatically produced H₂S in the presence of citric acid as capping agent leads to the generation of Ag/Ag₂S NPs. UV-vis spectroscopy is employed to characterize absorbance spectra of resulting Ag/Ag₂S NPs with the highest signal-to-noise ratio at 385 nm. Enzymatically produced Ag/Ag₂S NPs are characterized by TEM, XPS, DLS and XRD. This new colorimetric method was applied to the detection of enzymatic activity of GOx (LOD 0.557 μg mL⁻¹ and linear range up to 1.5 μg mL⁻¹). The effect of D-glucose on the read-out signal has been studied to confirm the enzymatic mechanism of this process (LOD 176.21 μM and linear range up to 1.25 mM) and was applied to the detection of glucose in human plasma.

Introduction

Nanomaterials exhibit very interesting electrical, optical, magnetic and chemical properties, which are not shown by their bulk equivalents. Nanoparticles have high surface area to volume ratios and their shape can be tailored by varying concentrations of their precursors and capping agents. In recent years nanomaterial based analytical assays have attracted much attention due to their versatility, high sensitivity and inexpensive fabrication of new devices for the detection of a wide range of analytes. Among the nanomaterials, both metallic and semiconductor nanoparticles (NPs) are considered to be the most broadly utilized structures in bioanalytical assays and biosensors. Their exceptional physicochemical properties, easy structure and shape determination and their nanoscale sizes similar to those of some biomolecules make them promising structures for their use as labels, transducers and amplifiers in biosensing.^[1]

Silver sulfide nanostructures such as NPs, quantum dots and nanostructured films possess unique optical and electrical properties. They have been intensively investigated in the recent years and their several applications such as infrared detectors,^[2] photoconductors, semiconductors in solar cells^[3] or fluorescent labels in biology and medicine^[4] were reported. Moreover, aqueous colloidal solutions of silver sulfide nanoparticles (Ag₂S NPs) are considered to be much less toxic in comparison to other commonly used nanomaterials such as PbSe, PbS, CdS, and CdSe QDs, holding particular promise for biological applications.^[5]

Ag₂S NPs have been prepared by numerous methods that include hydrothermal and sol-gel routes,^[6,7] solvo-thermal methods,^[8] hydrochemical bath deposition,^[9–11] micro-emulsion methods^[12] and electrochemical methods.^[13] A number of procedures are based on the strong interaction between silver and sulfide ions in aqueous/organic solutions that tend to form solid and stable structures in an easy and fast way. While a simple silver salt is typically used as silver source (i.e.: AgNO₃), various organic and inorganic sulfides are used to provide sulfide ions, including H₂S, alkyl thiols^[14] or (NH₄)₂S.^[15,16] Capping agents, on the other hand, are used to control particle size, shape and stability. Moreover, capping agents are an important factor also in controlling toxicity of Ag₂S NPs. Different capping agents such as mercapto-derivates,^[15,17,18] triton X-100,^[14] PVP and citrate^[9–11] have been used to stabilize NPs. Although, the above mentioned procedures present some advantages and produce particles with particular properties, they often require harsh preparation conditions, toxic solvents, they are time consuming, suffer from energy consumption and large size distribution. Hence, finding routes for production of Ag₂S NPs under physiological conditions compatible with biological proteins is a challenging task.

The use of biological agents like enzymes in bioanalytical assays is receiving a lot of attention nowadays. Enzymes are proteins with catalytic properties and high specific activity. The products of enzymatic reactions can interact with nanomaterials, resulting in modification of their measurable

properties.^[19] Normally two main approaches are followed: modulation of nanoparticles or growth in situ. On one hand, enzymatic reactions generate specific products that can enhance or decrease the NPs read-out signal as the result of their growth,^[20] quenching^[21] or etching.^[22] This procedure presents some advantages such as high sensitivity and versatility, but it requires the previous synthesis of the NPs. To overcome this issue, the in situ formation of nanomaterials as a result of an enzymatic reaction is presented as the best alternative. Increasing number of publications in bioanalysis is dedicated to the use of enzymes for the in situ formation of nanoparticles as the read-out signal mainly due to their optical^[23] and electrochemical^[24] properties. This approach maintains the advantages of the previous strategy and also avoids the need of pre-synthesized nanoparticles simplifying the bioassay.

Enzymatic in situ production of silver containing NPs can find broad application in bioanalysis because enzymes are extensively employed for detection of analytes and amplification of the read-out signal. Given the fact that the silver containing NPs strongly absorb UV and visible light, their in situ formation, triggered by an enzyme, can be conveniently followed by UV-vis spectroscopy.

In this work we propose a simple enzymatic method for the synthesis of Ag/Ag₂S spherical nanoparticles in an aqueous solution in the presence of citrate ions as capping agent. This present system based on formation of Ag/Ag₂S NPs was applied to the detection of enzymatic activity of glucose oxidase (GOx) and the detection of glucose in real samples. This system was selected considering glucose importance in clinical for diabetes management. During the last decades, glucose biosensor technology including point-of-care devices, continuous glucose monitoring systems and noninvasive glucose monitoring systems have been significantly improved^[25,26] and great efforts have been made to achieve better accuracy, precision and sensibility by using different techniques (colorimetry,^[27,28] photoelectrochemistry,^[29] electrochemistry^[30]). Here we present an easy colorimetric method that could be integrated in a smartphone application for a rapid, easy and cost-effective determination of the desired analyte. Some recent studies have been developed in this direction for a

wide range of bioanalytical substances.^[31–34] To the best of our knowledge, enzymatic assays based on biocatalytic generation of silver sulfide NPs have never been reported before.

Results and discussion

Chemical synthesis of Ag/Ag₂S NPs

First, the optimal experimental conditions for the growth of Ag/Ag₂S NPs from Ag⁺ and S²⁻ ions in aqueous citrate buffer, suitable for operation of GOx, were determined. As it is known, citrate acts as a capping agent and stabilizer for inorganic NPs.^[9–11] The formation of Ag₂S nanospherical moieties is almost instant in the presence of low concentrations of Ag⁺ and S²⁻ ions in aqueous solutions as one can conclude from very low solubility product constant of Ag₂S ($K_{sp} = 6.3 \times 10^{-50}$).^[35] Aqueous solutions of Ag/Ag₂S NPs are colored dark yellow. The intensity of color depends on the amount of Ag/Ag₂S NPs in the media and color turns brownish at high concentrations of NPs (Figure 1a). The absorbance spectrum of the synthesized NPs agrees well with literature data showing a broad band between 350 and 400 nm (Figure 1b).^[16,36] No absorbance of UV-vis light was observed in the spectra of aqueous solutions containing only AgNO₃, Na₂S or citric acid, respectively. This indicates that the absorbance spectrum of Ag/Ag₂S NPs is not influenced by the optical properties of individual reagents (Figure S1). Next, the selection of optimal wavelength for optical measurement was performed in order to obtain the best signal-to-background ratio of readings observed in the absence (Abs₀) and the presence (Abs) of Ag/Ag₂S NPs. According to the plot in Figure 1c, representing the ratio Abs/Abs₀ vs. wavelength, the highest ratio of Abs/Abs₀ was observed at the wavelength of 385 nm.

Figure 1 a) Change in color of reaction mixtures with increasing sulfide concentration, b) Absorbance spectrum of citrate buffer 10 mM pH 4 (dashed line) and synthesized Ag/Ag₂S NPs (solid line), c) Signal-to-background ratio between absorbance spectra of Ag/Ag₂S and citrate buffer 10 mM pH 4.

To optimize concentrations of reagents, varying amounts of S²⁻ and Ag⁺ were mixed up in the citrate buffer (10 mM, pH 4). The registered optical signals are directly related to the increase in the concentration of one of the precursors when the concentration of the other precursor was fixed, as depicted in Figure 2a, Figure 2c and in Figure S2. In case of Na₂S, the increase in its concentration causes the increase in the intensity of the absorbance peak, which asymptotically approaches maximum value starting from 0.5 mM (Figure 2b). For AgNO₃ the saturation starts from 2 mM (Figure 2d). The absorbance intensity reaches a maximum at stoichiometric concentrations of reagents (AgNO₃:Na₂S, 2:1) in all cases. The initial solution was completely transparent and upon addition of the second reagent the mixture turned dark yellow. This change in color is caused by the formation of colloidal Ag/Ag₂S nano-spheres up to the stoichiometric relation, where one of the reagents is completely consumed. Beyond this point, there was no change in color, reaching a plateau. In order to test the response of the system, a number of control experiments were carried out (Figure 2b and Figure 2d, red line). No absorbance was observed in the absence of one of the precursors hence it was confirmed that the appearance of color is caused by the formation of colloidal Ag/Ag₂S NPs in citrate buffer at room temperature.

Figure 2 a) Abs/Abs₀ ratio of the system containing AgNO₃ (1 mM) and different concentrations of Na₂S: a) 0 mM, b) 0.1 mM, c) 0.25 mM, d) 0.5 mM, e) 1 mM. b) Calibration curve of Na₂S in the absence (red) and presence (black) of AgNO₃ (1 mM). c) Abs/Abs₀ ratio of the system containing Na₂S (1 mM) and different concentrations of AgNO₃: a) 0 mM, b) 0.25 mM, c) 0.5 mM, d) 1 mM, e) 2 mM, f) 4 mM, g) 8 mM. d) Calibration curve of AgNO₃ in the absence (red) and presence (black) of Na₂S (1 mM).

The other parameter optimized was the concentration of citrate ions acting as capping agent and reductant of silver ions.^[37,38] The three carboxylate groups of citrate have a strong affinity to silver ions, favoring the stabilization of small Ag₂S NPs and thus avoiding their agglomeration into large structures.^[9,10] On the other hand, the reducing capacity of citric acid is well known and used in a wide number of syntheses. For that reason it is crucial to determine the proper conditions for the growth of Ag/Ag₂S nanospherical moieties and its possible reductant behavior to form spherical Ag NPs. The influence of varying concentrations of citrate (from 0.25 to 10 mM) on the absorbance at 385 nm demonstrated by mixtures containing AgNO₃ (1 mM) and Na₂S (from 0 to 1 mM) is shown in Figure S3. The maximum absorbance signal, registered immediately after injection of all three components, was apparently reduced when citrate concentrations were increased reaching 25% drop in the signal intensity at 10 mM citrate concentration. Nevertheless, the solutions of Ag/Ag₂S NPs prepared in the presence of 10 mM citrate demonstrated higher stability (data not shown). Taking into account the

increased stability of Ag/Ag₂S NPs in the presence of higher concentrations of citrate ions and the increased buffer capacity required for prospective biological applications, 10 mM citrate was selected as an acceptable concentration of the capping agent and buffer for subsequent measurements. The effect of pH on the amount of Ag/Ag₂S NPs formed in situ was studied too. As depicted in Figure S4, the increase in the absorbance is related with the decrease in pH from 5 to 3, enhancing the signal almost in 60%. Even though acidic media apparently favors formation of more Ag/Ag₂S NPs in the assay mixture, low pH compromises stability of proteins and other biopolymers. Thus, citrate buffer at pH of 4 was used in the following experimental work. This value was also selected considering that the optimum pH range for the glucose oxidase is between 3 and 5.

Another aspect to point out is the stability on Ag/Ag₂S NPs produced under physiological conditions. The effect of different incubation times on absorbance measured at varying concentration of S²⁻ and fixed concentration of Ag⁺ was studied. As it can be seen in Figure S5, the absorbance remains almost constant even for incubation times up to 12 hours indicating that Ag/Ag₂S NPs are stable in the 10 mM buffered citrate solution (10 mM, pH 4). It was decided to establish 3 min as incubating time for the all the following experiments. Finally, optimization of Ag⁺ concentration needed for quantification of sulfide ions was carried out. As shown in Figure S6, the best signal/background ratio was achieved at AgNO₃ 1 mM.

Considering the above-mentioned experimental data, the following optimal parameters for enzymatic generation of Ag/Ag₂S NPs were used in subsequent experiments: AgNO₃ 1 mM, citrate 10 mM, pH 4, incubation time 3 min, measuring wavelength 385 nm.

Ag/Ag₂S NPs characterization

TEM images displayed in Figure 3 confirmed the presence of spherical Ag NPs formed after 3 min under physiological conditions at different concentrations of S²⁻. Even when the sulfide ions were not present in the reaction mixture, spherical Ag NPs were observed with a medium diameter of 9 nm

(Figure 3a). When sulfide concentration was increased to 0.25 mM, NPs of a different geometry were observed. They are composed of two different materials since they present different contrast in TEM imaging. Once again spherical Ag NPs with higher contrast were detected with the medium diameter of 9 nm but they are connected to Ag₂S moieties of the same diameter, and lower contrast (Figure 3b).

According to the histograms, diameter of the Ag NPs does not significantly change when sulfide concentration is increasing in the media. Under our experimental conditions, Ag NPs serve as crystallization centers for growth of Ag₂S NPs attached to the surface of Ag NPs yielding Ag/Ag₂S NPs. TEM images reveal the mechanism of Ag/Ag₂S NPs formation. This is, some silver ions are immediately reduced by citrate ions forming seeding spherical Ag NPs, then sulfide anions and silver cations form Ag₂S NPs on the surface of seeding Ag NPs. The resulting NPs have lengths up to 18-19 nm and an average diameter of 9 nm. This structure of silver cores interconnected through silver sulfide moieties has also been presented in recent works.^[39-41]

Figure 3 TEM images and size distribution of Ag cores obtained at different Na₂S concentrations: a) 0 mM, b) 0.25 mM.

The NPs size in solution was determined by DLS measurements as it is included in Figure S7. The aggregation of Ag NPs in solution is appreciable when no sulfide is present in the media reaching diameter sizes of 115 nm or bigger. On the other hand, when adding sulfide smaller NPs are stabilized as the concentration is increased up to 30 nm as the concentration is increased. The slight change in diameter between TEM images and DLS measurements might be due to the different behavior of the NPs in solution and in solid state regarding the hydrodynamic diameter. The presence of the capping agent leads to a stabilization of the NPs in solution, therefore, avoiding their agglomeration, as it has been previously demonstrated in literature.^[9-11]

Glucose oxidase assay

Having optimized our colorimetric system for detection of sulfide ions based on rapid formation of Ag/Ag₂S NPs we coupled it with an enzymatic system producing hydrogen sulfide. We used the oxidation of the artificial substrate 1-thio- β -D-glucose with oxygen catalyzed by GOx to produce D-gluconic acid and hydrogen peroxide. This enzyme has been widely used and studied since the early 1950's^[42] due to its relatively low cost and good stability. GOx has seen large-scale technological applications in chemical, pharmaceutical, food, beverage, clinical chemistry, biotechnology and other industries.^[43] In addition, this enzyme is the mostly used biorecognition element in bioanalysis mainly for specific and sensitive determination of glucose. It operates in concert with other enzymes or nanoparticles^[44] and can be immobilized on different substrates in bioreactors and biosensors.^[45] In order to fabricate reproducible biosensors for glucose the initial enzymatic activity of GOx aqueous solutions should be quantified. According to the standard enzymatic assay for GOx from Sigma-Aldrich its activity is determined with an assay mixture containing an additional horseradish peroxidase (HRP) enzyme that is used for the detection of H₂O₂ produced by GOx in the course of oxidation of D-glucose with oxygen. Our approach allows avoiding the use of HRP as described in Scheme 1. GOx catalyzes the oxidation of the artificial substrate 1-thio- β -D-glucose in presence of oxygen to gluconic

acid and hydrogen sulfide. The latter readily interacts with silver ions in the presence of citric acid, acting as a capping agent, to yield Ag/Ag₂S NPs in situ. UV-vis spectroscopy is applied to follow the growth of Ag/Ag₂S NPs which strongly adsorb UV-vis light. The amount of generated Ag/Ag₂S NPs and consequently the observed optical signal are directly correlated with the enzymatic activity of GOx and concentration of 1-thio-β-D-glucose in the assay mixture.

Scheme 1 Colorimetric GOx assay based on detection of Ag/Ag₂S NPs formed enzymatically in situ.

The effect of increasing concentrations of 1-thio-β-D-glucose on the observed absorbance spectrum was studied. Figure 4a demonstrates the ratios (Abs/Abs_0) of the registered absorbance in the presence of varying concentrations 1-thio-β-D-glucose (Abs) to absorbance registered in the absence of 1-thio-β-D-glucose in the assay mixture (Abs_0). The plots of Abs/Abs_0 vs. wavelength reveal that the maximal ratio of the readout signal to the background signal was reached at 385 nm. Figure 4b depicts the influence of increasing 1-thio-β-D-glucose concentrations on the absorbance signal registered at 385 nm (Abs_{385nm}). As one can notice in Figure 4b the increase in 1-thio-β-D-glucose concentration is directly related to the increase in the intensity of absorption peaks at 385 nm. This calibration curve shows linearity from 0 to 0.5 mM and saturation starting from 0.55 mM of substrate concentration. It means that the number of Ag/Ag₂S NPs generated is directly related with the quantity of 1-thio-β-D-

glucose in the reaction mixture. According to the shape of the curve this biocatalytic reaction is consistent with typical Michaelis-Menten kinetic model.

Figure 4 a) Abs/Abs₀ ratio of the system containing AgNO₃ (1 mM), GOx (95 μg mL⁻¹) and different concentrations of 1-thio-β-D-glucose: a) 0 mM, b) 0.05 mM, c) 0.1 mM, d) 0.15 mM, e) 1.25 mM, f) 0.5 mM, g) 0.75 mM, h) 1.25 mM in citrate buffer 10 mM pH 4. b) Calibration curve of 1-thio-β-D-glucose in absence (red) and presence (black) of AgNO₃ (1 mM).

The experimental data were fitted by nonlinear regression method according to the Michaelis-Menten equation $Abs_{385} = Abs_{max385} [S] / (K_M + [S])$, where $[S]$ is the concentration of 1-thio-β-D-glucose and K_M is the apparent Michaelis-Menten constant equal to 256.1 ± 1.02 mM. The IUPAC definition was used to determine the limit of detection (LOD).^[45] This enzymatic colorimetric assay for 1-thio-β-D-glucose detection showed a LOD equal to 4.82 μM. The average relative standard deviation (RSD) calculated from the 1-thio-β-D-glucose calibration plot was 8.46% (unless otherwise specified, RSD was always acquired utilizing not less than three independent measurements). The shape of the calibration plot in Figure 4b implies that the saturating concentration of 1-thio-β-D-glucose is 1 mM. This concentration of the artificial substrate was used to evaluate enzymatic activity of GOx by optical detection of resulting Ag/Ag₂S NPs.

Figure 5 a) Abs/Abs₀ ratio of the system containing AgNO₃ (1 mM), 1-thio-β-D-glucose (1 mM) and different concentrations of GOx: a) 0 μg mL⁻¹, b) 0.28 μg mL⁻¹, c) 0.57 μg mL⁻¹, d) 0.95 μg mL⁻¹, e) 1.42 μg mL⁻¹, f) 1.9 μg mL⁻¹, g) 2.85 μg mL⁻¹, h) 6.66 μg mL⁻¹ in citrate buffer 10 mM pH 4. b) Calibration curve of GOx in the absence (red) and presence (black) of AgNO₃ (1 mM).

The effect of varying GOx concentrations on the absorbance response observed at saturating 1 mM concentration of 1-thio-β-D-glucose is depicted in Figure 5. Figure 5a represents the ratios (Abs/Abs₀) of the registered absorbance in the presence of varying concentrations GOx (Abs) to the absorbance recorded in the absence of GOx (Abs₀) in the assay mixture vs. wavelength. Once again, the highest ratio was reached at 385 nm. Figure 5b demonstrates the calibration curve obtained by plotting the intensities of absorbance at 385 nm (Abs_{385nm}) against GOx concentration. The LOD for GOx in the linear range (from 0 to 1.5 μg mL⁻¹) was 0.557 μg mL⁻¹. The average relative standard deviation (RSD) calculated from the GOx calibration plot (obtained using at least three independent measurements) was 7.09%. The standard assay for GOx requires the second enzyme HRP for detection of the resulting hydrogen peroxide. Our method does not use the second enzyme allowing simplification and decreasing the cost of GOx assays. Moreover, no enzymatic in situ growth of Ag₂S structures has ever been reported.

In order to provide more experimental evidence that silver cations constitute NPs in the enzymatic system control experiments were carried out in the absence Ag⁺ cations. No absorbance was detected when the concentration of GOx was fixed and the concentration of 1-thio-β-D-glucose was varied

(Figure 4b, red curve), neither when the concentration of 1-thio- β -D-glucose was fixed and the concentration of GOx was varied (Figure 5b, red curve).

TEM images displayed in Figure 6 shows the Ag/Ag₂S NPs enzymatically synthesized. Ag cores appear with more contrast surrounded by an amorphous unshaped product with a final average particle size of 11.78 nm due to the formation of Ag₂S moieties around the Ag cores. These results agree with the chemically synthesized Ag/Ag₂S NPs structures previously described. Furthermore, we carried out HR-TEM and electron diffraction analysis to identify the phase forming the cores and the unshaped material. Figure S8 shows a HR-TEM image from enzymatically synthesized Ag/Ag₂S NPs with the magnification of a selected nanoparticle and the interplanar distances from each moiety (a) and the electron diffraction pattern (b). From the HR-TEM images we can slightly distinguish two heteronanostructures containing two phases: monoclinic silver sulfide with α -Ag₂S acanthite structure and metallic cubic Ag. The lattice fringe spacing of 2.33 Å is consistent with the (111) lattice planes of the cubic metallic Ag and the one of 2.46 Å is associated with the (111) planes of the acanthite, the natural structure of Ag₂S at low temperatures.^[10,40,46,47] Electron diffraction analysis also showed the presence of crystalline Ag structures (reflection from (111) plane) and an amorphous shell associated to the Ag₂S moiety containing the reflection from the (-113), (031) and (120) planes. Comparing spacing values of their respective crystal structures it is found that the lattice interplanar distances of the monoclinic Ag₂S NPs are larger than those of the corresponding crystal planes of the fcc Ag NPs. Therefore, the increase in particle size from Ag NPs to Ag/Ag₂S NPs can be explained by the enlargement of lattice d-spacings as the structure changed.

Figure 6 TEM images and size distribution of enzymatically synthesized Ag/Ag₂S NPs.

Moreover, the chemical composition of enzymatically synthesized Ag/Ag₂S NPs was corroborated by EDX, XRD and XPS measurements. EDX spectra from enzymatically synthesized Ag/Ag₂S have been acquired in a transmission electron microscope and the data analysis is shown in Figure S9. These results confirmed the presence of elements Ag and S in the sample once filtrated and concentrated, indicating that the elements found can only be localized in the Ag/Ag₂S structures. Figure S10 shows the results from the XRD analysis of concentrated and dried samples. It can be seen two broad peaks in the range of Ag and Ag₂S signals attributed to the amorphous structure of the final material. These results agree with the HR-TEM and electron diffraction measurements confirming the presence of both crystalline and amorphous phases. Figure S11 presents the XPS results of two samples in presence and absence of the enzyme showing intense peaks at around 160.7 and 161.8 eV associated to the 2p 3/2 peak of Ag-S and S²⁻, respectively.^[48] The peak area associated to Ag-S and S²⁻ increase in the presence of the enzyme. On the other hand, the Ag peak 3d 5/2 shifts slightly at lower binding energies when Ag-S is formed. This shift corroborates the formation of Ag-S bonds only in presence of the enzyme.

Glucose assay

To validate the proposed enzymatic mechanism of Ag/Ag₂S NPs formation, the effect of the natural substrate D-glucose on the optical readout was studied. The natural substrate and the artificial one 1-thio-β-D-glucose compete for binding with FAD that is the active center of GOx. The influence of different amounts of D-glucose at fixed amount of 1-thio-β-D-glucose (1 mM) on absorbance is shown

in Figure 7. The decrease in the readout signal is directly related to the concentration of glucose added to the system. The response shows linearity from 0 to 1.25 mM and the LOD was found to be 176.21 μM . The average relative standard deviation (RSD) calculated from the glucose calibration plot (obtained using at least three independent measurements) was 2.08%.

Figure 7 Effect of glucose on the response of the assay mixtures containing of AgNO_3 (1 mM), 1-thio- β -D-glucose (0.5 mM) and GOx ($19 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) in citrate buffer 10 mM pH 4.

Given the fact that the normal levels in human plasma vary from 2.8 mM (hypoglycemia)^[49] to 7 mM (hyperglycemia),^[50] our method could be used in routine laboratories. Therefore, we applied our assay to the detection of glucose in human serum by employing the standard addition method. In this method, several serum samples of the same volume were distributed in separate eppendorfs and standard solution containing known glucose concentrations was injected. Thereafter, the same enzymatic reaction as before was followed and the absorbance was measured. The concentrations of respective standards (x -axis) were plotted against their corresponding absorbance signal (y -axis). A linear regression analysis was performed to calculate the intercept of the calibration curve with the x -axis, representing the concentration of glucose in the serum (Figure 8). Taking into consideration all sample

dilutions, the concentration of glucose was established at 6.02 mM, which lies within the limits of normal glucose level in human serum.

Figure 8 Quantification of glucose in human plasma with the method of standard addition. The system contained AgNO_3 (1 mM), 1-thio- β -D-glucose (0.5 mM) and GOx ($19 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) in citrate buffer 10 mM pH 4.

Although recent works have reported better limits of detection for glucose like some electrochemical^[29,30] or colorimetric methods,^[27,28] they usually require sophisticated devices or protocols, long procedure times, expensive reagents or the previous synthesis of the materials to use. Moreover, as it can be seen in Table S1, the majority of the colorimetric methods are based on the change of color from a chemical substrate^[51,52] or due to a morphological change of nanoparticles.^[53,54] These procedures need the use of pre-synthesized structures and/or a second reactive as a read-out signal to be able to follow the reaction. In our case, our protocol does not require the previous synthesis of the nanoparticles because we synthesized them in situ, what makes it easier and enables to gain time. Moreover, the Ag/Ag₂S nanoparticles serve as read-out signal themselves because of their intrinsic color, so no additional color-sensitizer is required. Finally, the procedure proposed has demonstrated to be sensible enough for glucose detection in real samples with no pre-treatment needed.

Conclusions

In summary, a rapid and easy procedure for preparation of stable Ag/Ag₂S spherical nanoparticles in an aqueous buffered solution under physiological conditions is reported. The mild conditions of this process allowed us to couple it to the biocatalytic oxidation of 1-thio-β-D-glucose catalyzed by glucose oxidase. The resulting optical assay for enzymatic activity of GOx is much simpler and faster than the standard activity test relying on the second enzyme HRP and the dangerous carcinogenic substrate o-Dianisidine. GOx activity, limits of detection and dynamic range were determined showing similar or better results than fluorogenic and photoelectrochemical procedures previously developed. Moreover, we have demonstrated the applicability of this system for glucose detection in real samples.

This colorimetric method is cost-effective, allows for real-time measurements and does not require sophisticated instruments. To the best of our knowledge this is the first enzymatic synthesis in situ of silver containing NPs with analytical applications.

Supporting Information Summary

Experimental details, reagents and solutions, instrumentation, enzymatic procedures, calibration of citrate, pH, AgNO₃, stability, characterization section (DLS, HR-TEM, EDX, XRD, XPS) and glucose sensing methods comparative table are included.

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Keywords

Biosynthesis, glucose detection, glucose oxidase, Ag₂S nanoparticles, UV-Vis spectroscopy.

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TOC

Facile, fast and direct enzymatic biosynthesis of silver/silver sulfide nanoparticles and their subsequent optical detection is presented. Glucose oxidase was employed for the enzymatic growth and modulation of Ag/Ag₂S in aqueous solutions with inexpensive reagents at room temperature. The Ag/Ag₂S nanoparticles enzymatically produced were applied to sensitive colorimetric assays for enzymatic activity and glucose determination in real samples.

